

**DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF COMFORTABLE GARMENTS FOR
BREASTFEEDING MOTHERS IN MAKURDI METROPOLIS, BENUE STATE.**

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to identify problems encountered by breastfeeding mothers emanating from garment, appropriate garment designs for breastfeeding mothers, to identify and develop appropriate prototype breastfeeding garments for comfort, fit and acceptability by breastfeeding mothers. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted the Survey Research, Research and Development (R&D) to collate the data needed for analysis and the construction of prototype garments. The population of the study comprised of 519 breastfeeding mothers registered in five (5) Government hospitals in Makurdi metropolis between 21st March and 26th April, 2016. A sample of 226 breastfeeding mothers was proportionally selected from the five hospitals. The findings of the study revealed that Dresses without easy access to breast make the babies frustrated during breastfeeding; the silhouette of garments can determine breastfeeding in some place; dresses with openings and closures positioned at the back inconvenience the breastfeeding exercise. The study also identified the garment styles preferred by Breastfeeding Mothers: The Buba and the Tight Fitted Garment were most highly accepted among breastfeeding mothers; while the 2 Piece Garment, Loose Fitted Garment and Gown were highly accepted. The study concluded that the extent to which a designed and constructed garment would be acceptable is directly related to its comfortability, fit and concealment features. The study suggested that a further research be carried out on the Impact of Breastfeeding garments on Exclusive Breastfeeding.

Key words: Design, comfort, breastfeeding, silhouette.

Introduction

Breast feeding is the natural way of feeding the young infants, thus providing numerous health benefits for both the mother and her infants (UNICEF, 2001). Breast milk is very crucial to early physical, mental and immunological development of babies (WHO, 2000). The World Health Organization (WHO) states that breast milk is the ideal food for the healthy growth and development of infants. Breast feeding is also an integral part of the reproductive process with important implication for the health of mothers (Samour, 2012). WHO together with UNICEF recommended exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life, after which the WHO's guidelines recommend continued breastfeeding until two years of age or beyond. Similar recommendations hold for both developed and developing countries and these recommendations focus on preventing gastrointestinal infections as well as providing optimal conditions for maintaining the child's normal weight and cognitive development. Breastfeeding is a complete nutrition that is easy for the body to digest, which

promotes the child's eating more often due to faster digestion. Indeed, the federal government of Nigeria has advocated exclusive breastfeeding among breastfeeding mothers with a view to reduce malnutrition and other related conditions that lead to high infant and child mortality in the country (The Info Stride, 2012). The success rate among mothers who want to breastfeed can be greatly improved through active support from their families, health care leaders, clinicians, employers, educational organizations communities and policy makers and effective breastfeeding clothing. Given the importance of breastfeeding, its clothing must be suited for the health and well being of mother and child.

Design and construction of comfortable garment for breast feeding mothers have been given little or no consideration. The privacy for mother and child while breastfeeding in public needs special consideration and attention. Smith (2013) states that, breast feeding is not an excretory function and there is no reason to hide when you feed your baby. The researcher has over a long period of time keenly observed the difficulties faced by breastfeeding mothers in their efforts to breastfeed their babies particularly during public gatherings like weddings, naming ceremonies, political meetings, workshops/seminars and places of worship. This observed difficulties seems universal. Ford (2007) documents that mothers are uncomfortable about breastfeeding in the public. The researcher observed that breastfeeding mothers have to lift up their blouses and even gowns in attempt to have access to their breast for breastfeeding. For instance, a breastfeeding young mother went about with a large shawl which she tied on her waist, pulled up her short gown to conveniently breastfeed her baby while visiting people.

Consequently, the difficulties and the inconveniences of uneasy access to the breast cause many women not to breastfeed their babies at appropriate time to meet the milk demand by their babies. Uneasy access to breast makes some babies cry so much before they can have access to the breast milk. These difficulties, negatively affect effective breastfeeding which is medically recommended. Some babies may reject the breast milk as a result of lack of easy

access to breast, thereby making the child vulnerable to childhood diseases. This research therefore, aims at designing and constructing suitable garments for breastfeeding mothers, to enhance the convenient breastfeeding of their babies at all times and in all occasions.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to design and construct comfortable garments for breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to;

- i. identified problems encountered by breastfeeding mothers emanating from garments in Makurdi metropolis.
- ii. identified appropriate garment designs selected by breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis.
- iii. designed and developed prototype breastfeeding garment styles selected by breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis.

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the differences between young breastfeeding mothers (15 -19years) and older mothers (40 years and above) on fit, in Makurdi metropolis.
2. What are the differences between young breastfeeding mothers (15 -19years) and older mothers (40 years and above) on comfort, in Makurdi metropolis.
3. What are the differences between occupational status of breastfeeding mothers on acceptability of designed garments, in Makurdi metropolis.

Research Hypotheses

- i. H₀₁: There is no significant difference between responses of young breast feeding mothers (15-19 years) and older breast feeding mothers (40 years and above) on fit in Makurdi metropolis.
- ii. H₀₂: There is no significant difference between responses of young breast feeding mothers (15-19 years) and older breast feeding mothers (40 years and above) on comfort in Makurdi metropolis.
- iii. H₀₃: There is no significant difference between occupational status of breastfeeding mothers on acceptability of designed garments, in Makurdi metropolis.

Methodology

Area of Study: The study was carried out in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, in government registered hospitals. Makurdi LGA was created in 1976, it is located in Zone of B of Benue State, North Central. It has Latitude 7.74 ° North and longitude 8.51° East. The Local Government shares boundaries with Guma LGA to the North-East. The LGA is divided into two major blocks by river Benue, hence the North and the South banks. According to the 2006 census, Makurdi had a population of 226,198 with a landmass of 16km radius. Makurdi town, the head quarters of the Local Government also serves as the state capital. Its location can best be described as the “Gateway” of the state to both the North and South. The indigenous dwellers are Tiv, Idoma, Igede and other ethnic groups. Makurdi LGA is endowed with great investment potentialities both in agro-allied and mineral resources.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of breastfeeding mothers registered in Government hospitals in Makurdi metropolis totaling 519 women, between 21st March, 2016 and 26th April, 2016. (Field Data, 2016).

Sample of the Study

The sample of the study was drawn from the population of all breastfeeding mothers in the five selected medical institutions in Makurdi metropolis which included Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Federal Medical Center Makurdi, Epidemiology Center Makurdi, General Hospital North-Bank and Family Support Programme Clinic Makurdi, all with a total of 519 registered breastfeeding mothers. The sample size for each clinic was obtained using proportionate sampling technique for the population. 226 breastfeeding mothers were proportionally selected from the five hospitals. The entire population participated in the descriptive survey while only ten (10) volunteer breastfeeding mothers participated in Research and Development (R&D) process of the research.

Instrument for Data Collection

Breast Feeding Mother's Opinion Questionnaire (BFMOQ) was employed for collection of data. The questionnaire was divided into six sections.

Section A Sought information on the bio data of the respondents

Section B Acceptability of Constructed Garments by Breastfeeding Mothers

Section C Appropriate Features of Patterns Selected by Breast Feeding

Section D Comfortable Level of Constructed Garment by Breast Feeding Mothers

Section E Concealment of Breast by Breastfeeding Mothers while Breastfeeding

Section F Fitness Level of Designed and Constructed Garment by Breastfeeding Mothers

Spearman Brown reliability coefficient was used. A reliability coefficient of $r = 0.71$ was realized.

Data Collection and Analysis

Research Question 1

What are the differences between young breastfeeding mothers (15 -19years) and older mothers (40 years and above) on fit, in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 1: Assessment on Fit of Constructed Garment by Breast Feeding Mothers

Specimen	HF	F	FF	NF	Total	Mean	SD	Remark
Style 1 (fitted Garment)	6	2	2	0	10	3.40	0.79	Fitting
Style 2 (Loose fitted Garment)	5	3	1	1	10	3.35	0.81	Fitting
Style 3 (Buba)	6	4	0	0	10	3.60	0.87	Highly Fitting
Style 4 (2pieces garment)	4	4	2	0	10	3.20	0.65	Fitting
Style 5 (Gown)	6	3	1	0	10	3.50	0.85	Highly Fitting

Source: Field Data 2016.

Keys: MF-Most Fitting (4), F-Fitting (3), FF-Fairly fitting (2) and NF-Not fitting (1)

The table presented respondents assessment of the fitness level of the five designed and constructed garments for breastfeeding mothers which revealed that, Style 3 (Buba) and style5 (Gown) had mean value $\bar{x} = 3.60$ and $\bar{x} = 3.50$ and were the most fitting. And also the mean value of $\bar{x} = 3.40$; $\bar{x} = 3.35$ and $\bar{x} = 3.20$ for style1 (fitted Garment); style2 (loose Garment) and style 4(2 piece garment) respectively showed that they were well fitting.

Prototypes of Constructed Breastfeeding Garments for Nursing Mothers.

Style 1 (Fitted Garment)

Style 2 (Loose Fitted Garment)

Style 3 (Buba)

Style 4 (2 Piece Garment)

Style 5 (Gown)

Research Hypothesis 1:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between responses of young breast feeding mothers (15-19 years) and older breast feeding mothers (40 years and above) on fit in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 2: ANOVA Assessment on Fit of Constructed Garment by Breast Feeding Mothers

Source of variance	Sum of square	DF	Variance estimate	F-ratio	F-table	P	Remark
Between groups	19852.2	3	6617.4	124.43	3.24	<0.05	H ₀ rejected
Within groups	850.8	16	53.18				
Total	20703	19					

The obtained F-ratio of 124.43 was higher than the critical F-table value of 3.24; hence the null hypothesis was rejected.

Research Question 2

What are the differences between young breastfeeding mothers (15 -19years) and older mothers (40 years and above) on comfort, in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 3: Comfortability of Constructed Garments by Breastfeeding Mothers in Makurdi Metropolis.

Specimen	HC	C	FC	NC	Total	Mean	SD	Remark
Style 1 (fitted Garment)	5	3	2	0	10	3.30	0.75	Comfortable
Style 2 (Loose fitted Garment)	4	5	1	0	10	3.40	0.83	Comfortable

Style 3 (Buba)	5	3	1	1	10	3.30	0.76	Comfortable
Style 4 (2 pieces garment)	7	2	1	0	10	3.60	0.91	Highly Comfortable
Style 5 (Gown)	5	4	1	0	10	3.40	0.78	Comfortable

Source: Field Data 2016

Keys: HC-Highly Comfortable (4), C-Comfortable (3), FC-Fairly comfortable (2) and NC-Not comfortable (1)

The result on the comfortability of constructed Garments by breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis showed that “Style 4” (Two pieces of Garment) was highly comfortable with mean value of $\bar{x} = 3.60$ while “Style 2” (Loose fitted garment) had a mean of $\bar{x} = 3.40$; style 5 (Gown) $\bar{x} = 3.40$; Style3 (Buba) $\bar{x} = 3.30$ and “Style 1”(fitted garment) $\bar{x} = 3.30$ respectively were all comfortable on the breast feeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis.

Research Hypothesis 2:

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between responses of young breastfeeding mothers (15-19 years) and older breastfeeding mothers (40 years and above) on comfort, in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 4: ANOVA Test on Comfortability of Constructed Garments by Breastfeeding Mothers in Makurdi Metropolis.

Source of variance	Sum of square	DF	Variance estimate	F-ratio	F-table	P	Remark
Between groups	19444.2	3	6481.4	75.76	3.24	<0.05	H ₀ rejected
Within groups	1368.8	16	85.55				
Total	20813	19					

From the above, F-Calculated is 75.76 while F-Tabulated is 3.24 at 3 degrees of freedom at 5%

level of significance. Since the F-calculated is greater than the critical value, we therefore reject the null hypothesis.

Research Question 3

What are the differences between occupational status of breastfeeding mothers on acceptability of designed garments, in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 5: Acceptability of Constructed Garments by Breastfeeding Mothers in Makurdi Metropolis.

Specimen	HA	A	FA	NA	Total	Mean	SD	Remark
Style 1 (fitted Garment)	5	4	1	0	10	3.32	0.82	Acceptable
Style 2 (Loose fitted Garment)	5	3	1	1	10	3.35	0.76	Acceptable
Style 3 (Buba)	6	3	1	0	10	3.51	0.87	Highly Acceptable
Style 4 (2pieces garment)	4	4	2	0	10	3.23	0.65	Acceptable
Style 5 (Gown)	5	3	1	1	226	3.30	0.73	Acceptable

Source: Field Data 2016.

Keys: HA-Highly Acceptable (4), A-Acceptable (3), FA-Fairly Acceptable (2) and NA-Not Acceptable (1)

The result on the acceptability of constructed garment for breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis indicated that “Style 3” (Buba) (3.51) was most highly accepted by the breastfeeding mothers. “Style 2” (loose fitted Garment) (3.35), “Style 1” (fitted garment) (3.32); “Style 5” (Gown) (3.30) and “Style 4” (Two pieces of garment) (3.23) respectively were all highly accepted by breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis.

Research Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between occupational status of breastfeeding mothers on acceptability of designed garments, in Makurdi metropolis.

Table 6: ANOVA Test on Responses of Breast Feeding Mothers on Acceptability.

Source of variance	Sum of square	DF	Variance estimate	F-ratio	F-table	P	Remark
Between groups	16118.6	3	5372.87	110.58	3.24	<0.05	H ₀ rejected
Within groups	777.4	16	48.59				
Total	16896	19					

From the table above, $F_{\text{Calculated}}$ is 110.58 while $F_{\text{Tabulated}}$ is 3.24 at 3 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance. Since the F-calculated is greater than the critical value, we therefore reject the null hypothesis.

Discussion of Findings

This study revealed that Dresses without easy access to breast make the baby frustrated during breastfeeding. The style (overall shape) of the garment can determine breast feeding in some places, dresses with openings and closures at the back inconvenience the breast feeding exercise. The study also revealed that “tight fitted blouses” does not gives discomfort if there is appropriate concealment at the bust line for easy access to breast. Some mothers don’t like breast feeding in public, as documented by Ford (2007), that mothers are uncomfortable about breastfeeding in public. The result on the opinion of the respondents on the features of preferred garment design showed that, the most features of garments preferred by Breastfeeding Mothers were garment tight fitted blouse with Velcro at the princess line highly preferred, followed by Loose fitted blouses with Velcro at bust lines and blouse with

zip at both sides of the bust line. Others were blouse with Velcro for opening and closure at the position of bust line, blouse with zip across the bust line, blouse with zip at princess line, gown with zip across the bust line, blouse with Velcro at bust line, and Blouse with Velcro at both sides of the bust line, which were all fairly preferred. This is In line with Gough (2008) findings, that breastfeeding mothers need not fear of exposing their bust in the full glare of the public because the brassier section of the garments flexes shrinks and allows mothers the ease to bring out their breast and breastfeed their young ones. This is supported by Thurrow (1998) in (Taylor, 2013) who opined that for any garment to be accepted, it must meet up with the basic factors of design for the person or group it is intended for.

Conclusion

The research work showed that breastfeeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis were interested in appropriate garment designs that enable them breastfeed comfortably, without the exposure of their breast, back or tummy anytime, anywhere. The study further revealed that some breast feeding mothers in Makurdi metropolis were more comfortable with blouse designed with opening and closure at the bust line in order to make breastfeeding more comfortable for them. The data also indicated that majority of the breastfeeding mothers preferred tight fitted blouse with Velcro opening at the princess line, blouse with Velcro at bust line and loose fitted Blouses with Velcro at bust line.

Recommendations.

- i. Designers should produce buba and two pieces of garment as the most appropriate prototype garments for the breast feeding mothers.
- ii. Designers should produce mostly breastfeeding garments with Velcro opening at the Princess Line as the most preferred features of pattern selected by breastfeeding mothers.

- iii. Designers should produce mostly breastfeeding garments with Velcro and zip opening and closure at both bust Lines to allow for discreet and convenient breastfeeding anywhere anytime.
- iv. Breastfeeding mothers should include buba and two pieces garment in their wardrobe while breast feeding their babies as it gives more comfort and easy access to the breast.
- v. The information obtained from this research especially on garment choice by breastfeeding mothers should be produced in form of charts and given to fashion designer and tailors/seamstress in order to correctly produce the right garment for breastfeeding mother.

References

- Adamu, L. (2007). *The Baby-Friendly Initiative Programme: Taraba State Seminar/Workshop*. Min of Health – Jalingo, Nigeria. Pp 12.
- Akeredolu, A. M. (2000). History of Nigerian Costume. Ibadan: *NISER*, 19, 233-250.
- Ashdown, S.P., & DeLong, M.R. (1995). Perceptual testing of apparel variation. *Applied Ergonomics*, 26(1): 1 pp.47-54
- Campbell, T. (2004). *How Does Nursing Wear Make Breast-feeding Easier?* U. S. A: Nursing Wear. ABN 83098 240 670.
- Carroll, K. (2006). Disability its Effect on the Body, and the Clothing Perspective. Retrieved August, 2016, from <http://dx.doi.org/10.2752/BEWDF/EDch10712>
- Chang, N. (2007). How To Convert Your Own Clothes Into Nursing. Retrieved August, 2016, From <http://www.clothes/ettow.com/ettow/Hobbies/Games> and toys.htm
- Charles, & Louise, S. (2008). Clothing: Clothes Make the man, Retrieved August, 2016, from <http://www.wikiquote.com>
- Cole, D (2012), “A Review of Breastfeeding Literature Relevant to Osteopathic Practice”. *International Journal of Osteopathic Medicine* 14 (2): 61- 66.
- Breast Cancer and Hormone Replacement Therapy. Retrieved August, 2016, from www.ncbi.nlm.gov/pubmed/10213546
- Cox, A & Dittmar, H. (1995). *Clothing* (3rd edition). London: Macmillan Company.

- Cox, J. & Dittmar, H. (1995). The Functions of clothes and clothing (Dissatisfaction): A Gender Analysis Among British Students. *Journal of consumer Policy*, pp 237 – 9, 240 – 3.
- Craig, H.I (1968). *Clothing: A Comprehensive Study*. New York. T.B. Lippincolt.
- Das, A & Ishtiaque, S.M. (2004). Comfort and Characteristics of Fabrics Containing Twist-less and Hollow Fibrous Assemblies in Weft, *JTATM* 3 (4),1-7.
- Dhinakaran, M., Sundaresan, S., & Dasarada, B. S. (2011). Comfort Properties of Garments. *The Indian Textile Journal* 32, 2-10.
- Diana A. Agbo (2012). Functional Garment Needs of Physically Challenged Wheel Chair and Bedridden Females in Benue State Nigeria. *Journal of Education, Health and Technology Research* (NJEHETR).
- Dikko, H. (2006) Modification of Hijab for Working Women and Nursing Mothers in Northern Nigeria. (Unpublished work). A Thesis Submitted to the School of Postgraduate, Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria.
- Dodd, L.M (2004). *Haltered Cover Garment for Nursing Mothers*. Indianapolis, USA: New Albany.
- Elija, R.A (2011). Acceptability of Self-Constructed Garments for Breastfeeding Mothers in Taraba State. (Unpublished work). A Thesis Submitted to the School of Postgraduate, Ahmadu Bello University, Nigeria.
- Emaikwu, S.O (2006). *Fundamentals of Education Research Methods and Statistics*. Kaduna: Deray Prints Ltd.
- Exclusive Breastfeeding. (2013). Retrieved Aug., 2013, from www.theinfostride.com/forum/index.php?r=160231.0
- Ford, J (2007), How to Breastfeed in Public. Retrieved August, 2016, from <http://www.ettow.com/ettowparenting>.
- Thurow, T. M. (1998). *Family Clothing*. New York/London: John Willey and Sons Inc.
- Weber J. (1999), *Clothing, Fashion, Fabrics and Construction*. USA: Glencoe/MacGraw-Hill.
- WHO/ UNICEF, (2000). International Code of Marketing of Breast Milk Substitutes and Subsequent Relevant. Geneva World Health Assembly
- Workman, J.E., Lentz, E. S. (2000). Measurement Specification for fit Models as a Factor in Clothing Size Variation. *Clothing and Textiles Research Journal*, 10 (1), 31 - 36